

Dabra and Pathara shared $73 \pm 4\%$ similarity). Cluster analysis using only the 14 mapped markers linked to QTLs for root traits gave identical first- and second-level groups, as did analysis using only 16 mapped markers not linked to root QTLs. A further 34 markers, covering all 12 chromosomes, were screened on the two released varieties, Kalinga III and Sathi 34-36; 66% of them were polymorphic.

In the mapping population derived from Bala/Azucena, Azucena was the donor of positive alleles for four QTLs, while Bala was the donor for one QTL on chromosome 5. Kalinga III had the Bala-type locus for nine markers at QTLs on chromosomes 2, 7, 9, and 11. Because most Indian landraces had the Azucena locus in up to five of these markers, they could be used as donor parents for MAS to improve Kalinga III for root growth. Dabra, Ratta Chawal, and Sathi 34-36 had the Azucena allele at markers C601 (chromosome 2), RG650 (chromosome 7), and RG2 (chromosome 11).

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Dendrogram showing hierarchical (average linkage, between-group) clustering of varieties based on 110 RFLP bands.

Evaluation of *in situ* conservation of *Oryza rufipogon* populations using RAPD markers

Z.-W. Xie, S. Ge, K.-Q. Wang, D.-Y. Hong, Laboratory of Systematic and Evolutionary Botany, Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Beijing 100093; and B.R. Lu, GRC, IRRI E-mail: xiezw@public.east.cn.net

Oryza rufipogon Griff. is a perennial species widely distributed in the tropics and subtropics of monsoon Asia. It constitutes a valuable genetic resource for rice improvement (Chang 1984). This species once occurred in eight provinces and autonomous regions of China but it is now extinct in Fujian and is nearly extinct in Hunan and Jiangxi. An intensive biodiversity conservation program for *O. rufipogon* has recently been initiated in China, using the *in situ* approach, which has been regarded as an effective method

to maintain diversity of wild rice species in their original habitats (Vaughan and Chang 1992). Knowledge on genetic diversity, population structure, and dynamics of the target *O. rufipogon* populations is important for strategic design and effective management and conservation. Such information, however, is still very limited. This study aimed to estimate the genetic diversity of *O. rufipogon* populations and to confirm the *in situ* conservation sites for this species using random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers.

Six *O. rufipogon* populations from *in situ* conservation sites in China were investigated through field surveys during 1997-98. These populations were classified into four groups according to their origins (Table 1). Young and clean leaves of 15–18 individuals were sampled from different populations (Table 1). The method for sample collection, leaf preservation, and DNA extraction followed those described by Xie et al (1999). To prevent overestimating the genetic diversity by polymorphic loci variation, 20 primers (OPB 1–20

of kit B of Operon Technologies Inc.) were randomly chosen to analyze leaf samples, regardless of the polymorphism of amplified fragments. Only one primer (OPB-06) amplified unclear bands and was excluded from the experiment. The other 19 primers produced strong and reproducible fragments and thus were used for further analysis. RAPD fragments were scored as present (1) or absent (0) for each DNA sample to estimate genetic distance between individuals. Genetic diversity was measured by the percent polymorphic bands (PPB) at population and region levels. An analysis of molecular variation (AMOVA) was used to partition variance components among individuals of a population, among populations within a region, and among regions. All the analyses were

performed with the RAPDistance program (version 1.04) and WINAMOVA program (version 1.5). An unweighted paired group method for cluster analysis (UPGMA) using the genetic distance estimates was also used.

A total of 241 fragments ranging from 190 to 2,800 bp in size were scored in 100 individuals of the six populations studied. Each individual had a unique haplotype. PPBs for each population and region are shown in Table 2. AMOVA results showed highly significant genetic differentiation among regions and among populations of the same regions (Table 3). Considerable variation was detected within each of the six populations. The 100 individuals were clustered into six groups that corresponded to the six populations in-

cluded in this study. The major portion of the total genetic variation was identified within rather than between populations. These data can help in designing more strategic *in situ* conservation programs for *O. rufipogon* in China.

China established *in situ* conservation sites of *O. rufipogon* in Dongxiang county (populations PO2 and PO3) in Jiangxi Province in 1992. The Dongxiang populations are the northernmost populations in the entire distribution of this species. The two populations are located about 5 km from each other and have special characteristics such as cold tolerance. Five population-specific RAPD bands were identified in each population. The two populations also showed some differentiation based on cluster analysis of RAPD bands. The levels of genetic diversity of the two populations were moderately high among 29 Chinese *O. rufipogon* populations analyzed by Xie (1999). Therefore, it is necessary to independently conserve the two populations *in situ*.

Population PO5, located in Yangtianqiao of Guangdong Province, is particularly valuable. Individuals from this population have been extensively used for

Table 1. Populations of *Oryza rufipogon* used in this study.

Group code	Population code	Locality	Individuals sampled (no.)
GP1	PO2	Dongxiang, Jiangxi Province	15
	PO3	Dongxiang, Jiangxi Province	15
GP2	PO5	Yangtianqiao, Guangdong Province	18
	P19	Hanguang, Guangdong Province	18
GP3	P59	Heping, Guangxi Province	16
GP4	P47	Sanya, Hainan Province	18

Table 2. Number and percentage of polymorphic bands detected in each population and region.*

Primer	Bands (no.)	Polymorphic bands (no.)										Total
		PO2	PO3	GP1	PO5	P19	GP2	P59	GP3	P47	GP4	
OPB-01	14	3	6	6	5	8	8	2	2	5	5	9
OPB-02	12	3	3	3	6	7	8	6	6	9	9	12
OPB-03	15	6	5	7	9	7	11	3	3	5	5	12
OPB-04	15	4	5	6	3	4	5	5	5	4	4	13
OPB-05	15	2	3	3	1	3	4	3	3	8	8	12
OPB-07	12	4	5	5	3	4	6	5	5	6	6	10
OPB-08	14	4	4	6	5	7	9	4	4	7	7	13
OPB-09	10	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	9
OPB-10	10	5	4	6	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	9
OPB-11	13	4	7	8	7	6	7	5	5	5	5	12
OPB-12	12	5	3	6	6	6	8	2	2	4	4	8
OPB-13	13	4	3	5	5	6	9	3	3	5	5	10
OPB-14	8	0	2	2	2	3	4	1	1	3	3	7
OPB-15	12	4	5	6	5	7	9	3	3	5	5	10
OPB-16	6	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	6
OPB-17	18	3	6	7	9	9	12	6	6	6	6	15
OPB-18	12	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	10
OPB-19	14	5	4	7	6	4	8	2	2	5	5	11
OPB-20	16	4	5	6	5	6	7	2	2	9	9	11
Total	241	72	78	98	91	100	132	68	68	102	102	200
PPB	—	29.88	32.37	41.08	37.76	41.49	54.77	28.22	28.22	42.32	42.32	82.99

*Population codes = PO2, PO3, PO5, P19, P59, and P47; group codes = GP1, GP2, GP3, and GP4. PPB = percent polymorphic bands.

Table 3. Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) for 100 individuals of *Oryza rufipogon* from four different regions.

Source of variation	df	SSD	MSD	Variance component	% total variance	P value	Bartlett's statistic
Global							
Between regions	3	5.175	1.725	0.024	13.40	<0.001	2.638
Populations/region	2	2.256	1.128	0.063	34.73	<0.001	2.608
Individuals/population	94	8.799	0.094	0.094	51.87	<0.001	
Within regions							
Between populations	5	7.431	1.486	0.084	47.20	<0.001	
Within populations	94	8.799	0.094	0.094	52.80	<0.001	
Among regions							
Among regions	3	5.175	1.725	0.067	36.73	<0.001	
Within regions	96	11.054	0.115	0.115	63.27	<0.001	

SSD = sum of squared deviation, MSD = mean square deviation.

rice breeding since 1980. Some high-quality and high-yielding new rice varieties have been produced using *O. rufipogon* from this population as a parent in crossing programs. Considering its high genetic diversity as revealed by RAPD analysis (PPB = 38.15), this population needs to be conserved *in situ*.

Population P19, found in Hanguang, Guangdong Province, is one of the northern marginal populations in China. It has a much higher genetic diversity (PPB = 40.16%) than many of the 29 other populations studied by Xie (1999) and therefore is also a key population that needs to be conserved *in situ*.

One of the southernmost populations of *O. rufipogon* in China is population P47, located in Sanya of Hainan Prov-

ince. It occurs in a large pond near the sea and grows in brackish water. Because of the importance of maintaining some populations with special characteristics such as salinity tolerance, this population should be conserved *in situ*. In addition, the genetic diversity (PPB = 46.18%) of this population is the highest among the 29 populations studied.

Population P59 occurs on the upper reaches of a river in Heping, Guangxi Province, and is isolated from other *O. rufipogon* populations. RAPD analysis and previous analysis of data from 29 other populations showed that this population has a relatively low genetic diversity (PPB = 25.70) and no special characters. Therefore, this population could be maintained under *ex situ* conservation.

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Identification of genomic constitution of three tetraploid *Oryza* species through two-probe genomic *in situ* hybridization

C.B. Li, D.M. Zhang, S. Ge, and D.Y. Hong, Laboratory of Systematic and Evolutionary Botany, Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100093, China; and B.R. Lu, GRC, IRRI E-mail: licb@public2.east.net.cn

Two tetraploid *Oryza* species, *O. minuta* and *O. punctata* (with diploid and tetraploid types), are reported to contain the BBCC genomes based on the analysis of meiotic chromosome pairing at metaphase I of interspecific F₁ hybrids. *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri* have diploid and tetraploid forms. The genomic constitution of

tetraploid forms is still unclear. The genomic constitution of *O. malampuzbaensis* (treated as a synonym of *O. officinalis* by Vaughan 1989) was tentatively designated as BBCC, but no sound cytological data have been provided to support this designation.

Genome analysis based on observation of chromosome pairing has been largely challenged because chromosome pairing is known to be influenced by several factors including environmental and genetic ones, which have led to inaccurate measures of genomic affinities in some